

Generation of 2D enteroid culture

Note: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

- 1) Use fully grown 4-day old 3D enteroids in Complete Medium
- 2) Coat a 48 wells plate with DMEM/F12+1% Geltrex™ for 1h at 37°C
- 3) Eliminate the coating and let the plate dry for 10' under the hood
- 4) Remove the medium from 3D enteroids and collect them using ice cold DMEM/F12
- 5) Transfer in 15 ml falcon tube and spin 400 rcf for 5' at 4°C
- 6) Wash the pellet with ice cold PBSL in the same falcon tube
- 7) Spin 400 rcf per 5' at 4°C
- 8) Add 1ml TrypLE™ dissociation buffer every 10 wells of 3D enteroids
- 9) Vigorously pipet for 5-6 time with p1000 tip
- 10) Incubate in water bath for 10' at 37°C. Check the dissociation level under a light microscope. Do not overcome 10' of dissociation time
- 11) Add DMEM/F12+10%FBS prewarm (4 volumes for each ml of TrypLE™ previously used)
- 12) Count the number of cells in the suspension
- 13) Centrifuge the cells at 900 rcf for 5' at 4°C
- 14) Resuspend the pellet in the correct volume of Complete Medium to have a final concentration of 60.000 cells/well
- 15) Seed 400 µl of cell suspension in each well